

Kinetic And In Silico Evaluation Of Levamisole And Albendazole As Rat Hepatic Alkaline Phosphatase Inhibitors

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Abstract

Some conditions have been found to be associated with elevated levels of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) in the body, making the inhibition of this enzyme an area of significant interest in medical research. Levamisole has been recognized as an effective inhibitor of alkaline phosphatase, but the inhibitory potential of albendazole and their in silico interaction with alkaline phosphatase have not been fully explored. The aim of this study was to carry out kinetic and in silico evaluation of albendazole and levamisole on the hydrolytic activity of rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase. Spectrophotometric method was used to assay for the enzyme activity in the absence and presence of the drugs. Maximum rate of reaction (V_{max}) and Michaelis-Menten constant (K_m) were estimated using double reciprocal (Lineweaver-Burke) plots of the specific activity of the enzyme against the substrate concentration. In silico simulations utilized computational tools to predict the binding interactions of levamisole and albendazole with the active site of rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase. The presence of levamisole at 0.1% w/v slightly reduced the K_m of the enzyme from 0.824 mM to 0.783 mM while at 0.5% w/v and 1% w/v, the K_m of the enzyme increased from 0.824 mM to 1.286 mM and 1.086 mM respectively. The presence of albendazole at 0.1% w/v and 0.5% w/v increased the K_m of the enzyme from 0.824 mM to 0.857 mM and 0.885 mM respectively. The docking score, XP GScore and prime energy values of the interaction of levamisole with rat tissue non-specific (hepatic) alkaline phosphatase were -4.422, -4.504, and -20894.02 respectively while the docking score, XP GScore and prime energy values of the interaction of albendazole with rat tissue non-specific alkaline phosphatase were -2.894, -2.978, and 20963.88 respectively. Also, the study revealed that levamisole at 0.1% w/v non-competitively inhibited rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity while at 0.5% w/v and 1% w/v, inhibited rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity by mixed-type mode of inhibition. Also, it was revealed that albendazole at 0.1% w/v non-competitively inhibited rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity while at 0.5% w/v, inhibited rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity by mixed-type mode of inhibition and at 1% w/v, non-competitively inhibited rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity. The in silico evaluation showed that levamisole has a higher inhibitory effect compared to albendazole. This study demonstrates that levamisole is a potent inhibitor of tissue non-specific alkaline phosphatase while albendazole mildly inhibited the enzyme..

Keywords: Alkaline Phosphatase, Insilico, Albendazole, Inhibitors, Enzyme Kinetics

INTRODUCTION

Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) [phosphate-monoester phosphohydrolase (alkaline optimum); EC 3.1.3.1] enzyme is encoded by distinct genes as many tissue-specific isozymes (18). These isoenzymes are found on the outer layer of the cell membrane, and they catalyze the hydrolysis of organic phosphate esters found in the extracellular environment (17). It is found in several organisms like bacteria, plants, and animals (18). Essential co-factors of this enzyme include zinc and magnesium. Even though alkaline phosphatases are found in various body tissues and have various physiochemical characteristics, they are nonetheless true isoenzymes because they catalyze the same reaction (19). Alkaline phosphatase can be found, in decreasing order, in the placenta, ileal mucosa (intestine), kidney, bone, and liver. More than 80% of the alkaline phosphatase present in serum is secreted by the liver and bones, and to a lesser extent, the intestine (20). Alkaline

phosphatases are classified as tissue-specific and tissue-nonspecific types (12). Tissue-specific alkaline phosphatase refers to the isoforms of the enzyme that are predominantly found in specific tissues or organs. These isoforms are typically synthesized by cells in these tissues and are responsible for carrying out specialized physiological functions within those tissues (20).

Tissue 1 specific alkaline phosphatases can be found in the intestine, placenta and germinal tissues (11). Tissue non-specific alkaline phosphatase refers to the isoform of alkaline phosphatase that is present in multiple tissues throughout the body. They are expressed in various tissues, including the liver, bone, kidney, and intestine, and they are not limited to a particular tissue and are involved in more general functions (15). It has been established that medical conditions like cancer, liver diseases, and bile

obstructions are accompanied by increased alkaline phosphatase activity (14). This brings about the need to understand how certain compounds, like albendazole and levamisole, inhibit the action of alkaline phosphatase. Therefore, this study investigates the kinetic interactions of albendazole and levamisole on rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Drugs and Reagents Albendazole and Levamisole tablets were obtained from Medsoft Pharmacy, Marc, Tanke Rd, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. Each Albendazole tablet contained 200 mg of Albendazole, while each Levamisole tablet contained 40 mg of Levamisole. The substrate of alkaline phosphatase, Para-nitrophenylphosphate (p-NPP) was a product of Sigma-Aldrich Inc., St Louis, MO, USA. The buffer (Na₂CO₃ - NaHCO₃), sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and sucrose were of analytical grade and all solutions were prepared in standard volumetric flasks using distilled water. The reagents were stored in clean air tight containers of glass and plastic wares.

Experimental Animal

An adult male albino rat (*Rattus norvegicus*) was obtained from the Animal Holding Unit of the Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Methods

Preparation of Enzyme Source The male albino rat (*Rattus norvegicus*) weighing 250 g was sacrificed using cervical dislocation. The animal was quickly dissected and the required organ (liver) was harvested. The liver was cleaned by removing both the blood and fat. Then it was weighed using a weighing balance and suspended in isotonic 0.25 M ice-cold sucrose solution and refrigerated. The liver (10.49 g) was homogenized in ice-cold sucrose solution using mortar and pestle to avoid denaturation of the needed enzyme by the heat generated during the process. The homogenate was diluted to have a dilution factor of 1.33. The resulting homogenate was spun at 4,000 rev/min for 20 minutes. The supernatant was separated, plain sample bottles labeled accordingly and refrigerated at -4 °C until when it was needed.

Determination of Protein Concentration

The protein concentration was determined using the Biuret method of Gornall et al. (1949). Biuret reagent (4.0 mL) was added to 1.0 mL of the appropriately diluted tissue homogenate. This was mixed thoroughly by shaking after which it was left undisturbed for 30 minutes at room temperature (25°C) for colour development. The blank was

constituted by replacing the sample with 1.0 mL distilled water. The absorbance was read against the blank at 540 nm. Concentration of protein in the homogenate was calculated from the standard protein curve for bovine serum albumin. The curve was obtained by using varying concentrations of bovine serum albumin (2 -10 mg/mL).

Kinetic Evaluation of Rat Hepatic Alkaline Phosphatase Activity

Determination of Rat Hepatic Alkaline Phosphatase-catalyzed Hydrolysis of p-NPP The activity of alkaline phosphatase was assayed by monitoring the rate of hydrolysis of p-NPP at 25 °C in 0.1 M Na₂CO₃ - NaHCO₃ (carbonate buffer) pH 10.1 as described by Ahlers (6) and as outlined by Arise et al. (2008). Alkaline phosphatase catalysed the hydrolysis of phosphate group to yield para nitrophenol which is bright yellow in colour (other reactants and products are colourless in aqueous solution), the intensity of which is proportional to the activity of the enzyme. The activity of the enzyme was determined spectrophotometrically at 400 nm and expressed as mmol/min/mL. The reaction medium contained alkaline phosphatase and 0.1 M carbonate buffer of pH 10.1 which was incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes; after which p-NPP was added and incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes.

The reaction was then stopped with 0.35 M NaOH solution, after which absorbance was read at 400 nm against the blank. The protocol that was adopted for the determination of the activity of alkaline phosphatase-catalyzed hydrolysis of para nitrophenylphosphate is shown in Table 4 in Appendix I. 21 3.2.3.2 **Determination of the Effect of Albendazole on the Activity of Rat Hepatic Alkaline Phosphatase** The effect of albendazole on the activity of rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase was determined according to the following procedure. The reaction mixtures containing 0.2 mL of enzyme source, varying volumes of carbonate buffer (1.4 mL – 2.4 mL), 0.2 mL of 0.1% albendazole, was incubated at 25 °C for 10 minutes. Then varying volumes of 5 mM p-NPP (0.2 mL – 1.0 mL) were added to the reaction mixtures which were then incubated again at 25 °C for 10 minutes. After this, the reaction was stopped by adding 2.0 mL of 0.35 M NaOH, and the absorbance for each mixture was read at 400 nm against the blank. This procedure was repeated for two more sets of assays using 0.5% albendazole and 1% albendazole.

Determination of the Effect of Levamisole on the Activity of Rat Hepatic Alkaline Phosphatase

The effect of levamisole on the activity of rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase was determined according to the following procedure. The reaction mixtures

containing 0.2 mL of enzyme source, varying volumes of carbonate buffer (1.4 mL – 2.4 mL), 0.2 mL of 0.1% levamisole, was incubated at 25 °C for 10 minutes. Then varying volumes of 5 mM 2,2'-p-NPP (0.2 mL – 1.0 mL) were added to the reaction mixtures which were then incubated again at 25 °C for 10 minutes. After this, the reaction was stopped by adding 2.0 mL of 0.35 M NaOH, and the absorbance for each mixture was read at 400 nm against the blank. This procedure was repeated for two more sets of assays using 0.5% levamisole and 1% levamisole. The protocol that was adopted for the determination of the effect of levamisole on rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity is shown in Tables 8 - 10 in Appendix I. 3.2.4 In-Silico Evaluation of Interactions of Levamisole and Albendazole with Rat Hepatic Alkaline Phosphatase Molecular docking of Levamisole and Albendazole with rat non-specific (hepatic) alkaline phosphatase was carried out using the method described by (8) with slight modification.

Based on ligand-protein interaction, the binding affinity of the drug (Levamisole or Albendazole) as a ligand for the binding site of the marker enzyme was elucidated using AutoDock software version 4.2. Levamisole or Albendazole was docked into alkaline phosphatase-binding pocket applying standard procedure (22). Based on Lipinski rule of 5, Levamisole or Albendazole was docked with targeted alkaline phosphatase. The structures of these drugs were obtained from PubChem (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). Tertiary and 3D structures of target protein - alkaline 23 phosphatase were obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) and the molecular dynamics simulation software Gromacs version 5.1.2 (10). Molecular docking was carried out using AutoDock software version 4.2 and the results in terms of binding affinity were expressed as binding energy in kcal/mol. Each drug compound was docked into the enzyme-binding pocket to determine the protein-ligand interactions between the drug and the enzyme. Protein-ligand interactions between the drugs and target enzyme were analysed using PyMOL software version 2.0.2. 24.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the inhibitory effects of levamisole and albendazole on rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase (ALP) were investigated to assess their potential therapeutic applications and determine the type of inhibition they exhibit on the enzyme.

Levamisole Inhibition of Rat Hepatic Alkaline Phosphatase

The kinetic experiments revealed notable changes in the Michaelis-Menten constant (K_m) values and V_{max} values in the presence of levamisole, shedding

light on the mechanism of inhibition of the enzyme by this drug. As the concentration of levamisole was increased, the K_m and V_{max} values changed. Specifically, in the presence of 0.1% w/v levamisole, K_m reduced from 0.824 mM to 0.783 mM while V_{max} reduced from 588.24 mmol/min/mL to 434.78 mmol/min/mL, in the presence of 0.5% w/v levamisole, K_m increased from 0.824 mM to 1.286 mM while V_{max} reduced from 588.24 mmol/min/mL to 476.19 mmol/min/mL, and in the presence of 1% w/v levamisole, K_m increased from 0.824 mM to 1.086 mM while V_{max} reduced from 588.24 mmol/min/mL to 285.71 mmol/min/mL. Comparing the K_m values of the enzyme in the presence of levamisole, there is a general increase in the K_m values as the concentration of levamisole increases. K_m is a measure of substrate binding affinity for the active site of the enzyme, and an increase in the K_m value indicates a decrease in the substrate binding affinity, implying that the substrate binding step is affected (7). According to the Lineweaver-Burke plots, levamisole at 0.1% w/v non-competitively inhibited rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity while at 0.5% w/v and 1% w/v, inhibited rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity by mixed-type mode of inhibition.

Albendazole Inhibition of Rat Hepatic Alkaline Phosphatase

The presence of albendazole led to an increase in K_m values as its concentration increased. Also, as the concentration increased, the V_{max} values reduced. Specifically, in the presence of 0.1% w/v albendazole, K_m increased from 0.824 mM to 0.857 mM while V_{max} reduced from 588.24 mmol/min/mL to 476.19 mmol/min/mL, in the presence of 0.5% w/v albendazole, K_m increased from 0.824 mM to 0.885 mM while V_{max} reduced from 588.24 mmol/min/mL to 384.62 mmol/min/mL, and in the presence of 1% w/v levamisole, K_m reduced from 0.824 mM to 0.641 mM while V_{max} reduced from 588.24 mmol/min/mL to 256.41 mmol/min/mL. Comparing the K_m values of the enzyme in the presence of levamisole, there is a general increase in the K_m values as the concentration of levamisole increases.

These changes indicate that albendazole, too, primarily influences the substrate binding step (19). According to the Lineweaver-Burke plots, albendazole at 0.1% w/v non-competitively inhibited rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity while at 0.5% w/v, inhibited rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity by mixed-type mode of inhibition and at 1% w/v, non-competitively inhibited rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase activity (48). 5.3 In Silico Interactions of Levamisole and Albendazole with Rat Hepatic Alkaline Phosphatase.

According to Table 1b, levamisole exhibits a docking score of -4.422 and an XP GScore of -4.504, and its prime energy value of -20894.02 reflects the energy associated with the stable conformation of levamisole within the binding site. The MMGBSA moved residues indicate that residue HIS338 in chain A is involved in the binding interaction. The MMGBSA dG Bind value of -20.06 suggests a relatively favorable binding free energy, indicating a reasonably strong binding interaction between levamisole and rat tissue non-specific alkaline phosphatase(21). On the other hand, albendazole shows a docking score of -2.894 and an XP GScore of -2.978. The prime energy value of -20963.88 represents the energy associated with the stable conformation of albendazole within the binding site. The MMGBSA dG Bind value of 11.64 indicates a less favorable binding free energy compared to levamisole. The binding of levamisole to crystal structure rat non-specific alkaline phosphatase also involves a range of bond types and categories. These include hydrogen bonds, electrostatic interactions, carbon hydrogen bonds, electrostatic pi-cation interactions, pi-sulfur interactions, and hydrophobic pi-pi T-shaped and pi-alkyl interactions. Among these, the electrostatic salt bridge with a distance of 2.13217 Angstroms and the electrostatic pi-cation interaction with a distance of 3.96192 Angstroms are noteworthy. These interactions are crucial for ligand stabilization within 49 the binding site.

Amino acids such as ASP337, HIS171, HIS338, HIS341, HIS379, HIS451, and HIS454 play pivotal roles in these interactions, as indicated by the MMGBSA moved residues data. The negative values of the docking score (-4.422) and XP GScore (-4.504) once again highlight the favorable binding affinity. The prime energy (-20894.02) and MMGBSA dG Bind (-20.06) values signify the thermodynamic favorability of the interactions(21). Levamisole demonstrates a stronger binding affinity in both cases, as indicated by lower docking scores and XP GScores. This suggests that levamisole forms more stable complexes with rat non-specific alkaline phosphatase compared to albendazole (22). Electrostatic interactions, such as salt bridges and pi-cation interactions, play significant roles in stabilizing levamisole within the binding sites.

CONCLUSION

This study has been able to provide valuable insights into the inhibitory potential of levamisole and albendazole on rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase. Both drugs inhibit rat hepatic alkaline phosphatase, primarily affecting substrate binding. However, based on the computational data, albendazole was found to be a weaker inhibitor compared to levamisole, as a result of its lower binding affinity for the active site of the enzyme. The differential

strength of inhibition between levamisole and albendazole, as indicated by both kinetic and computational data, merits further investigation for their potential applications in the context of alkaline phosphatase-related medical conditions.

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